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In Vitro Interaction between Geminivirus Replicase Protein and the *Npr1* Gene Promoter from Chilli Pepper (*Capsicum annuum*)

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Abstract

The Geminivirus Replicase (*Rep*) protein has been suggested as one of the key determinants of the pathogenicity by suppressing the expression of *NPR1* gene as one of the key regulators in Systemic Acquired Resistance (*SAR*) during pathogen invasion. The aim of this study was to investigate the interaction possible between the *Rep* protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter. The experiment was conducted using Electrophoretic Mobility Assay (*EMSA*) approach between Core and Distal promoter and *Rep* protein, verified using Western Blot Analysis. This study successfully showed interaction between both molecules through *in-silico* and *in-vitro* analysis. The interaction was observed only between the *NPR1* gene distal promoter particularly on 2nd Fragment (*PD_CbNPR1-F2*). *In-silico* analysis using *HDOC* software obviously exhibited that the most likely interaction is located at *PD_CbNPR1-F2.4* segment indicated by the highest docking score and *rsmd* ligand (-176.56 and 26.80 Å respectively). Thus, this finding is in line with our above hypothesis regarding binding activity between the *Rep* protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter.

Keywords: *SAR*, Replicase, *EMSA*, *In-vitro* Interaction, *NPR1*-gene

Abbreviation: *CP_CbNPR1*-core promotor of Non-expressor Pathogen-Related Resistance 1; *PepYLCV*-Pepper Yellow Leaf Curl Virus; *PD_CbNPR1*- distal promotor of Non-expressor Pathogen-Related Resistance 1; *Rep*-Replicase

INTRODUCTION

Pepper Yellow Leaf Curl Virus (*PepYLCV*) belongs to the geminivirus family and is regarded as one of the destructive phytopathogenes in chilli cultivation. In West Sumatera, the *PepYLCV* infection has been reported since the last two decades, reported from the year of 2013; the virus infection significantly reduced up to 97% of fruit yield (Jamsari and Pedri, 2013).

The *PepYLCV* constitutes 5-7 substantial proteins that are necessary for viral replication, encapsulation, transmission and pathogenicity (Hanley-Bowdoin et al., 2013). Two different *PepYLCV*, mono- and bipartite have been reported to be existing in West Sumatera (Sakata et al., 2008; Jamsari and Pedri, 2013). The previous study suggested that monopartite isolates called *PepYLCtdV.TDWS21*(*TDWS21*) and *PepYLCpsV.PSSWS14* (*PSSWS14*) showed different pathogenicity levels. Whole-genome comparison from both isolates showed relatively similar for most genes compared in nucleotide level (99%). Interestingly, *Rep* gene showed homology 5% lower than others. Henceforth, the *Rep* gene was suggested to be a key factor in the pathogenicity of *PepYLCV* (Jamsari et al., 2016).

A recent study suggested that *Rep* protein will associate with retinoblastoma-related protein (*RBR*) and proliferating cellular nuclear antigen (*PCNA*). Both molecules were claimed as the central of host replication machinery in *TGMV* *Nicotiana* (Sahu et al., 2014). Furthermore, the *Rep*-*RBR* complex leads to negative regulation of cell cycle thereby reproducing viral particles (Singh and Singh, 2018). Moreover, *Rep* protein also

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has been reported in giving intervention effect thereby interacting with AUX/IAA protein PHYTOCHROME-ASSOCIATED PROTEIN 1 (PAP1), where virus could take over the plant phytohormonal signaling pathway in order to reduce plant immunity activation. Such interaction is also considered to happen with the *Non-Expressor of Pathogenesis-Related Gene1 (NPR1)* is a central regulation in plant immunity system (Ma and Ma, 2016).

Here we report, our successful expression of Rep protein originated from PepYLCV-PSSWS14, a pathogenic geminivirus in *E. coli* cell. Using EMSA assay combined with Western-Blot analysis we successfully also detected a complex binding between Rep protein and a segment of the distal promoter of the *NPR1* gene using chemiluminescence-labeled visualization. Taking into consideration, our data successfully indicated possible mechanisms of plant immunity suppression during PepYLCV infection that could bring idea to the plant immunity improvement.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Isolation of complete *NPR1* gene promoter sequence

Genomic DNA was extracted from young leaves of chili pepper genotype *Berangkai* following the procedure described by Jamsari and Pedri (2013). The distal promoter segment was previously isolated by Jamsari et al. (2019) and the complete sequence has been deposited with accession number NC_029983.1 in the NCBI database. While the core promoter was isolated using a series of primers and similar PCR conditions used for distal promoter segment isolation. The complete sequence of core promoter has also been deposited at NCBI database under accession number MK_310185.

Plasmid pET-28a (+)-Rep construction and transformation

The *Rep* gene was cloned into vector pET-28a (+) (Invitrogen, USA) using *Bam*HI and *Sac*I cloning sites. Successive protocol was performed as recommended by Thermo scientific following procedure as follow: ligation was performed in total reaction of 10 μ L (2 μ L 10x Ligase Buffer, 1 μ L 100 mM DTT, 2 μ L 10 mM ATP 8,6 μ L, 50 ng/ μ L pET-28a(+) vector, 0,4 μ L T4 DNA ligase, ligase dilution 2 buffer, 6 μ L gen Rep (0,2 pmol). The recombinant plasmid was then transformed into *E. coli* strain BL21 by employing heat shock method.

Expression, purification and detection of Rep protein

In order to get the maximum quantity of Rep protein, we investigated some factors affecting Rep protein expression, i.e., IPTG concentrations, culture temperature and culture duration. Four levels of IPTG concentrations from 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 mM and two different temperatures 18 °C and 28 °C, as well as four different duration of culture (3, 6, 9 and 12 hours), were applied in the protein induction experiment. The transformant bacteria were grown in a selective medium containing LB-Broth, 30 μ g/mL Kanamycin with pH 7.5. The culture was maintained in agitation of 150 rpm until reached OD₆₀₀ 0.6 prior induction experiment. The bacterial cell was then harvested and resuspended in 0.25x volume of cold Tris-HCl (pH 8,0) and lysed by freeze-thawing with buffer lysis (50 mM HEPES pH 7,4 150 mM KCL, 1 mM EDTA pH 8,0). The sample was centrifuged and the supernatant was subsequently transferred and homogenized in 0.5x volume Ammonium acetate-ethanol and finally incubated at -15 °C for overnight. Afterward, the protein was diluted in 0.25 of 80% Acetone, depleted and finally diluted in sample rehydration buffer. The Rep protein was purified using MagneHis Protein Purification System (Promega-USA) following protocol suggested by company. Protein concentration produced from each experiment was measured spectrometrically using Bradford standard and visualized using 12% SDS-PAGE. The Rep protein was transferred onto a nylon membrane using western blot and detected by chemiluminescence detection system with Penta-His primary and secondary antibody and Rabbit-anti-mouse IgG/AP-conjugate (Thermo scientific-USA) respectively. The membrane was exposed by X-ray (Siemens Multix X-Ray) under KV of 40 at 3.2 Mas to visualize Rep protein provided at M. Djamil General Hospital-Padang.

***In vitro* interaction of Rep protein and NPR1 gene promoter sequence**

In-vitro interaction between Rep protein and NPR1 gene promoter sequence was performed using EMSA protocol provided by Invitrogen-USA. Four fragments (PD_CbNPR1 (F1-2); CP_CbNPR1 (F1-2)) representing NPR1 distal and core promoter was analyzed in this study (See Table 3). A cocktail containing 1:1 ratio of Rep protein and *NPR1* gene promoter sequence containing 2 μ L from each of protein (150 ng/mL) and *NPR1* gene promoter sequence (150 ng/mL) was diluted in binding solution. The cocktail was incubated for 20 minutes and loaded before running in 8% Native-SDS gel under 200 Volt for 30 minutes. The gel was then stained using 1X SYBR® Green EMSA staining solution for 3 hours for DNA staining. Successively gel was stained by SYPRO® Ruby EMSA for another 3 hours. Every staining was visualized on UV-Transilluminator (Analytic Jena-Germany). The image obtained from every staining step was overlaid appropriately.

In-silico analysis of Rep-NPR1 gene promoter Interaction

Modeling prediction of Rep protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter sequence was simulated using 3D Dart (<http://milou.science.uu.nl/services/3DD-ART/>) and Phyre2 using the protocol as described by Kelley et al., (2015). *In silico* interaction between protein Rep and the *NPR1* gene promoter was predicted using HDOC (Yan et al., 2017). Due to the limited length capacity of the software, the promoter fragment was divided into seven segments; each segment has 500–600 nucleotides in length.

RESULTS**Characteristic of the *NPR1* gene promoter**

The complete regulatory sequence of the *NPR1* gene promoter consisted of distal and core segment was successfully isolated, spanning 11,004 bp in length located upstream from the start codon of its structural *NPR1* gene. Detail structure of the distal promoter and the cis-acting elements harboring along the sequences have been previously described by Jamsari et al. (2019). We further isolated the *NPR1* gene core promoter sequence using similar genotype and similar approach. The isolated core promoter segment covered 5,950 bp in size spanning from base 112,600,897 to base 112,606,847 (based on chromosome 7 of *Capsicum annuum* cv. *Zunla-1* (accession number: NC_029983.1) (Qin et al., 2014). Further detail nucleotide comparison with its reference sequence could identify 18 base polymorphisms along the obtained core sequence. The polymorphisms are mainly caused by base substitution and insertion-deletion (indel) events. Detail base variations between the core promoter sequence and its reference are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Polymorphism found along the core promoter of the *NPR1* gene from genotype Berangkai (CP_CbNPR1) and *Zunla-1*

No	Polymorphism Type	CP_CbNPR1	<i>Zunla-1</i>	Base position upstream (-) from ATG(-)
1.	Indel	A	-	12
2.	Indel	A	-	13
3.	Substitution	C	A	303
4.	Substitution	A	C	304
5.	Substitution	G	A	306
6.	Substitution	A	G	307
7.	Substitution	A	G	310
8.	Substitution	G	T	325
9.	Substitution	G	T	327
10.	Substitution	C	T	379
11.	Substitution	A	T	386
12.	Substitution	C	A	405
13.	Substitution	G	T	435
14.	Substitution	T	A	471

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15.	Substitution	T	A	474
16.	Indel	T	-	489
17.	Substitution	C	A	491
18.	Indel	-	T	1.431

Expression of Rep Protein

Effect of IPTG concentration and culture duration on the total protein concentration in two different temperatures during Rep expression was measured using Bradford method (data not are shown). The highest concentration (0.624 mg/mL) was produced at 28 °C after being induced with 1 mM IPTG, while culture at 18 °C for 9 hours could produce the highest total intracellular concentration compared to other treatments (see Fig. 1A-1B).

To verify the existence of Rep protein, detection using the Penta-His antibody was used to hibridize the target fragment. One single fragment with molecular weight of about 40 kDa could be obviously detected (Fig. 1C).

Figure 1. Effect of IPTG concentration and culture duration in different culture temperature on the protein expression. A: effect of IPTG concentration, B: effect of culture duration, C: Western blot of Rep protein verification.

Rep Protein-NPR1 Gene Promoter Sequence Interaction

EMSA assay was applied in order to verify binding activity between the Rep protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter sequence. Binding between both molecules is indicated by increasing molecular weight, which was caused by complex molecules formed between Rep protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter sequence. In vitro assay between Rep protein with the two segments of NPR1 gene core promoter (C1 and C2) exhibited no interaction between Rep protein and both two core promoter sequences indicated by their far migration from the start point in the EMSA assay (Fig 2A).

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Figure 2. EMSA-based assay to investigate binding activity between Rep protein and the *NPR1* gene promoter sequence. A: Binding analysis between Rep protein and segment C1 and C2 generated from a sequence of the *NPR1* gene core promoter, B: Binding analysis between Rep protein and segment D1 and D2 generated from segment of the *NPR1* gene distal promoter. Red box: free Rep protein; yellow box: free DNA; white box: complex Rep/PD_CbNPR1-F2) (C1: CP_CbNPR1-F1, R/C1: Rep-CP_CbNPR1-F1, C2: CP_CbNPR1-F2, R/C2: Rep-CP_CbNPR1-F2, D1: PD_CbNPR1-F1, R/D1: Rep-PD_CbNPR1-F1, D2: PD-CbNPR1-F2, R/D2: Rep-PD-CbNPR1-F2)

However, interesting fragment visual is exhibited from Fig 2B, where fragment migration of the R/D2 is slower than its counterpart R/D1, indicating that complex binding between Rep protein and D2 segment was really happening. This data obviously provide a new evident, that the Rep protein could bind interact with the *NPR1* gene distal promoter. In order to support our EMSA data, we performed docking simulation between the Rep protein with 7 segments generated from the distal promoter sequence. Each from the 7 segments has 500 bases in size except the last segment PD_CbNPR1-F2.7 (Table 3). That approach was applied due to sequence length capacity able to be processed by the HDQC software. Score docking and Ligand rmsd value from each simulation in every model are listed in the Table 2.

Three models of possible interaction are suggested from each binding between Rep protein and promoter fragment. Fragment DP_CbNPR1-F2.4 exhibited the lowest value of score docking from all the three models ranging from -169.10 to -176.56. Interestingly, the ligand rmsd value from their three models exhibited the lowest value ranging from 26.80 to 1205.68. Based on that both values, binding interaction of Rep protein was most likely possible with DP_CbNPR1-F2.4 than with other 6 fragments

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Table 2. Docking score generated by HDOCS software from segments of distal *NPR1* gene promoter

Fragment	Model	Score Docking	Ligand rmsd (Å)
DP_CbNPR1-F2.1 1-500 bp	I	-178.06	184.77
	II	-176.11	658.49
	III	-172.56	154.47
DP_CbNPR1-F2.2 501-1.000 bp	I	-167.67	1658.24
	II	-164.80	874.63
	III	-164.10	1249.17
DP_CbNPR1-F2.3 1.001-1.500 bp	I	-176.58	1162.29
	II	-173.32	1191.49
	III	-172.23	775.95
DP_CbNPR1-F2.4 1.501-2.000 bp	I	-176.56	26.80
	II	-171.01	1205.68
	III	-169.75	773.27
DP_CbNPR1-F2.5 2.001-2.500 bp	I	-175.81	422.77
	II	-172.37	986.47
	III	-168.52	948.84
DP_CbNPR1-F2.6 2.501-3.000 bp	I	-171.40	1194.59
	II	-169.57	1479.34
	III	-167.84	1127.64
DP_CbNPR1-F2.7 3.000-3.354 bp	I	-172.61	497.55
	II	-171.81	463.25
	III	-168.68	312.61

In order to get the overview of molecular binding between Rep protein and the fragment PD_CbNPR1-F2.4 in 3 dimension viewpoint, analysis using 3D Dart (<http://milou.science.uu.nl/services/3DD-ART/>) continued with Phyre2 was performed. The 3D model of interaction between the Rep protein and the fragment of PD_CbNPR1-F2.4 is presented in Fig 3.

Figure 3. In silico modelling of the interaction between Rep protein and fragment PD_CbNPR1-F2.4 generated by 3D Dart and Pyre2.

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Figure 3A demonstrated that the Rep-PD_CbNPR1-F2 interaction could occur. The interface position could be found in consensus sequence TTAAAAG located in between 112,603,012-112,605,020 and on the position of amino acid Thr¹⁷, Ala⁴⁷, Gln⁴⁸, Glu⁴⁹, Lys⁵⁰, Leu⁵⁶, Val⁶⁰, Thr⁸³, Phe⁸⁷, and Asn⁹⁰.

DISCUSSION

Expression induction of Rep protein was conducted under several optimization factors (Figure 1A and 1B). We found that Rep was upregulated under certain condition particularly in 0.6 mM IPTG at -18 °C. A similar result has been reported on the increase of elastase production that reached 142.889 U/mL in IPTG concentration of 0.6 mM. However a gradual decrease happened when the concentration increased from 0.8 to 1.0 mM IPTG (Shamsudin, 2017). At least, this result showed that the IPTG could successfully increase the expression of *Rep* under optimal concentration of IPTG (0.6 mM) at 18 °C for 9 hours that can be used as a reference for future experiments dealing with *Rep* protein expression.

We showed the successful of Rep protein purification from the bacterial cell (*E. coli*) insufficient relative quantity by employing affinity chromatography approach. The success of this method is supported by detection system using histidine-based tagging using a specific antibody and secondary antibody which is amenable for proper detection using chemiluminescence platform. Light emission produced by antibody complex enables one to be evaluated using an X-ray film (Alegria-Schaffer, 2014). Such procedure could assure the purity of the produced Rep protein.

Considering its crucial function in ETI and SAR signaling cascade toward biotic and biotic stress, the NPR1 is regarded to be a center of regulatory apparatus in plant defense mechanisms. Variation of the NPR1 protein concentration level due to different expression capacity is associated with the plant immunity status. In this respect, regulatory elements also known as promoter is regarded to be responsible for the molecular interaction especially during regulation expression of many genes (Hernandez-Garcia and Finer, 2014). A mutation on the particular NPR1 promoter sequence, like in the W-Box, constantly reduced its sensitivity to the SA accumulation (Saleh *et al.*, 2015). Shao *et al.* (2013) revealed that the *NPR1* gene core promoter from poplar contained RAV1AAT and W-box element recognized respectively as RAV1 and WRKY where specific protein will bind in responding to the SA accumulation upon pathogen infection. Another important element is WLE1, a domain found in OsPR1 promoter where the OsWRKY6 protein forms a complex binding. Hence, it is known as a positive regulator of SA responsiveness associated with pathogen-related genes activation (Choi *et al.*, 2015). Rationally, any modification of such regulatory elements might build a new perspective in empowering plant defense systems toward wide range of phytopathogens including PepYLCV (Withers and Dong, 2016).

Interaction between Distal Promotor and Rep prototein highly likely happen in the lowest score of rmsd (26.80Å) (Hevener *et al.* 2009). The point interaction was in consensus of TTAAAAG located in 112,603,012 - 112,605,020 based of reference. Based on Cis-regulatory analysis in PLACE the consensus represented DOFCOREZM protein recognition site, which regulated to protoplast etiolation. In addition, this protein is also responsible for pathogen infection response (Yanagisawa and Schmidt, 1999). We found binding formation was strikingly matching to the interaction Hyperthermophile protein (Iazp) act as a scaffold to dictate DNA structure as described by Luscombe *et al.* (2000), which related to the β -hairpin/ribbon proteins binding mode.

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REFERENCE

- i. Alegria-Schaffer A, 2014. *Western blotting using chemiluminescent substrates Methods in enzymology Elsevier*. 541:251-259.
- ii. Choi C, Hwang SH, Fang IR, Kwon SI, Park SR, Ahn I, Kim JB and Hwang DJ, 2015. *Molecular characterization of Oryza sativa WRKY6, which binds to W-box-like element 1 of the Oryza sativa*

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- pathogenesis-related (PR) 10a promoter and confers reduced susceptibility to pathogens. New Phytologist. 208.3:846-859.*
- iii. Hanley-Bowdoin L, Bejarano ER, Robertson D and Mansoor S, 2013. Geminiviruses: masters at redirecting and reprogramming plant processes. *Nature Reviews Microbiology. 11.11: 777-788.*
- iv. Hernandez-Garcia CM and Finer JJ, 2014. Identification and validation of promoters and cis-acting regulatory elements. *Plant Science. 217: 109-119.*
- v. Hevener KE, Zhao W, Ball DM, Babaoglu K, Qi J, White SW and Lee R.E, 2009. Validation of molecular docking programs for virtual screening against dihydropteroate synthase. *Journal of chemical information and modeling, 49: 444-460.*
- vi. Jamsari J, Oktavioni M, Nova B, Candra IA, Asben A and Syukriani L, 2019. Conserved structure of the NPR1 gene distal promoter isolated from a chili pepper (*Capsicum annum L.*) in West Sumatera. *F1000Research. 8:52.*
- vii. Jamsari J and Pedri J, 2013. Complete Nucleotide Sequence of DNA A-like Genome and DNA-B of Monopartite Pepper Yellow Leaf Curl Virus, A Dominant Begomovirus Infecting *Capsicum annum* in West Sumatera. *Asian Journal of Plant Pathology. 7: 1-14.*
- viii. Kelley LA, Mezulis S, Yates CM, Wass MN and Sternberg MJ, 2015. The Phyre2 web portal for protein modeling, prediction and analysis. *Nature protocols. 10: 845-858.*
- ix. Luscombe NM, Austin SE, Berman HM and Thornton JM, 2000. An overview of the structures of protein-DNA complexes. *Genome biology. 1.1. reviews001.*
- x. Ma K-W and Ma W, 2016. Phytohormone pathways as targets of pathogens to facilitate infection. *Plant molecular biology. 91: 713-725.*
- xi. Qin C, Yu C., Shen Y, Fang X, Chen L, Min J, Cheng J, Zhao S, Xu M, Luo Y and Yang Y, 2014. Whole-genome sequencing of cultivated and wild peppers provides insights into *Capsicum* domestication and specialization. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 111: 5135-5140.*
- xii. Sahu PP, Sharma N, Puranik S, Muthamilarasan M and Prasad M, 2014. Involvement of host regulatory pathways during geminivirus infection: a novel platform for generating durable resistance. *Functional & integrative genomics. 14: 47-58.*
- xiii. Saleh A, Withers J, Mohan R, Marqués J, Gu Y, Yan S, Zavaliev R, Nomoto M, Tada Y and Dong X, 2015. Posttranslational modifications of the master transcriptional regulator NPR1 enable dynamic but tight control of plant immune responses. *Cell host & microbe. 18: 169-182.*
- xiv. Shamsudin NH, 2017. Tight Repression of Elastase Strain K Overexpression By Pt7 (A1/04/03) Shuttle Expression System. *Galeri Warisan Sains. 1: 20-22.*
- xv. Shao Y, Zhang H, He H, Cheng B and Xiang Y, 2013. Molecular Cloning and Characterization of Orthologues of NPR1 Gene from Poplar. *Journal of Phytopathology. 161: 35-42.*
- xvi. Withers J and Dong X, 2016. Posttranslational modifications of NPR1: a single protein playing multiple roles in plant immunity and physiology. *PLoS pathogens. 12:1-9.*
- xvii. Yan Y, Zhang D, Zhou P, Li B and Huang S-Y, 2017. HDOCK: a web server for protein-protein and protein-DNA/RNA docking based on a hybrid strategy. *Nucleic acids research. 45: 365-373.*
- xviii. Yanagisawa S and Schmidt RJ, 1999. Diversity and Similarity among Recognition Sequences of Dof Transcription Factors. *The Plant Journal, 17.2: 209-214.*
- xix. Singh A and Singh IK, 2018. *Plant-Virus Interactions. Molecular Aspects of Plant-Pathogen Interaction, Springer, Singapore.*